

8- Theory to Reason Short Formation Time and the Spiral Structure of Galaxies

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Abstract:

By analyzing the framework of the 8-theory and in particular the coupling constant Equation and the N_V representation It becomes clear that insights regarding the formation of galaxies can be extrapolated. The short time regarding their formation can be explained by interactions after the electric, which are immensely stronger than the gravitational. The next coupling constant is only 6.65 weaker than the electric and can be reason as the missing link to their formation, so does the additional elements in the series.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (5)$$

Notice the first requirement: $\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0$

In addition, the second requirement: $\delta g = 0$

Those two simple requirements combined together can allow us to a deep Insight into the structure of galaxies. In the 8-theory framework, we have a Lorenz manifold, the manifold has areas of extremum curvature that stay as they are over time. That is given by the first requirement. The manifold also experience arbitrary variations, the second requirement. Those arbitrary Variations vanish into matter in agreement with a stationary Lorentz manifold.

The combination of both condition than implies that in order for the areas of extremum Curvature to stay as they are, the arbitrary variations cannot appear inside them. That is by the combination of the two requirements. However, those arbitrary variations still appear in the framework. In addition, the areas of Extremum curvature are a vital part of this theory. The combination of both requirement is than resulting in areas of extremum curvatures surrounded by arbitrary variations that could not affect them.

The following model of the 8-theory is than intersecting with the large scale geometrical shape of galaxies. However, it is known that so called, black holes in the center of galaxies are absorbing matter and nothing can escape them. So in a Second glance the first requirement will not hold in such case. However, that is not a real problem if we assume that those black holes, which we regard as areas of extrunum curvature inside galaxies also omit matter. We know it is the case, similar to what is known in physics as the "hawking radiation" $-\delta g(H)$.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} + \delta g + (-\delta g(H)) = 0 \quad (6)$$

So overall those two simple requirements in our framework provide an Interesting indication to structure of large-scale matter formations in the universe. The hawking radiation is a vital part of making the two conditions hold true. For each unit of fermions absorbed or manifested inside the area of extremum curvature we require a hawking radiation Particle emitted from the area, so the first requirement will hold true. The short time of formation can be reasoned by the coupling constant and the interactions after the electric, which are immensely stronger than the gravitational and in so, must be taken into account as significant in mega scale formations.

$$\frac{850}{128} = 6.65 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{9254}{128} = 72.3 \quad (8)$$

These are the next two after the electric, 6.65 weaker and 72.3 weaker and as the coupling constant series indicate there are many more interactions before the gravitational, which up to this day were completely ignored in the analysis of cluster formations of fermions.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)